

Let's Find Out: Why do Users React Differently with Applications Infused with AI Algorithms?

APPENDIX A:

Table 1. Descriptive statistics

Variables	Group					
	AI infused app game experience			Dyadic game experience		
	Mean	St	Median	Mean	St	Median
Excitement (E)	3.54	1.794	3.50	6.54	.859	7.00
Anger (Ag)	2.58	1.793	2.00	1.35	.629	1.00
Desire (Dr)	6.19	1.132	7.00	6.62	.571	7.00
Happy (H)	3.42	1.629	3.00	5.77	.704	7.00
Relaxation (R)	3.62	1.791	3.50	6.50	1.273	7.00

Table 2. Hypothesis test

Hypothesis	Partial correlations (P); effect size (r)
(H1) Playing with AI infused apps will lead to less excitement and thus generate different behavioral responses.	p<0.001; r = 0,744824 (****)
(H2) Playing with AI infused apps will lead to frustration among users, triggering anger experiences and thus generating different behavioral responses.	p<0.05; r = 0,381356 (****)
(H3) Increased feeling of desire "to win" while playing against the AI coupled apps evoke different behavioral response.	p < 0.264; r = 0,1549 (n)
(H4) The interpersonal communication, other DSE entities resulting from human to human game experience will have influence on happiness generating positive behavioral response than the game experience with an AI coupled game.	p < 0.001; r = 0,58715 (****)
(H5) Having human opponent during game experience makes player relaxed than having an AI coupled game.	p < 0.001; r = 0,717505 (****)
Note: large effect is .5, a medium effect is .3, and a small effect is .1.	
n) not significant, *) Statistically significant at p<0.1, **) Statistically significant at p<0.05, ***) Statistically significant at p<0.01, ****) Statistically significant at p<0.001	